

DECADAL CLIMATE PREDICTION PROJECT

Terms of Reference

Drafted: 2024.07.05

Confirmed by WGSIP and effective as of: 01.12.2024

This document complies with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) and ensures that the Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP) of the Working Group on Subseasonal to Interdecadal Prediction (WGSIP), itself part of the Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) Core Project, has in place transparent, accountable, and effective procedures which honour the commitment and contribution of volunteering individuals, and ensure fairness, inclusion, and equity. Should the WCRP, WGSIP and/or Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) Core Project guidelines change, this document will be updated.

Please refer to the [WCRP Procedural Terms and Definitions](#) for an explanation of the terms used in this document.

Purpose

1. The DCPP is the Decadal Climate Prediction Project of the ESMO Core Project of WCRP. WGSIP is the parent body of the DCPP.
2. The DCPP was initiated in 2009.
3. The goal of the DCPP is to enhance the accuracy of climate predictions over decadal timescales. By improving the understanding and design of initialised coupled Earth system prediction systems, the DCPP seeks to achieve skillful forecasts of temperature, precipitation, and other variables, leveraging external forcings like greenhouse gases and aerosols as well as predictability of internal climate variability.
4. Objectives of the DCPP:
 - 4.1. Design and organise coordinated decadal prediction (including retrospective) experiments, in conjunction with the seasonal prediction and climate modelling communities, and produce a comprehensive archive of results for research and applications
 - 4.2. Produce experimental quasi-operational decadal climate predictions in support of multi-model annual to decadal forecasting (including those lead by the WMO LC-A2DP) and apply the forecasts to societal needs
 - 4.3. Organise and coordinate decadal climate predictability studies and case studies of particular climate shifts and variations, including the study of the mechanisms that determine these behaviours with a focus on predictability and mechanisms
 - 4.4. Liaise with the Working Group on Subseasonal to Interdecadal Predictions, the Working Group on Numerical Experimentation and other relevant groups through the WCRP Modeling Advisory Council and other channels as appropriate;
 - 4.5. Report to WGSIP and ESMO as directed, and brief other relevant WCRP committees and panels on progress, status, and plans for activities overseen by the DCPP.

Term

5. The DCP, as a panel of WGSIP, remains active until a decision is made to close it by the WGSIP co-chairs or ESMO SSG.

Membership

TYPES & DECISION MAKING

6. There are 3 types of members: voting members, ex-officio members and emeritus members. All members with voting rights must be employed by an organisation/institution.
 - 6.1. A voting member of an ESMO body (Task Teams excluded) can not hold more than one voting membership within ESMO.
 - 6.2. Voting members have voting rights in all matters
 - 6.3. Ex-officio members have no voting rights but if the decision is relevant to them they can be invited to speak, at co-chairs' discretion, before the vote is made.
 - 6.4. Emeritus members have no voting rights.
 - 6.5. Where the Body's objectives include operational decisions, funding or resource recommendations and/or implementation activities it is suggested that the ToRs also include this Conflicts of Interest clause in addition to the required clauses number 20, 30 and 43 in this document.

Members of [Body] will:

 - have regard to the [IPO/PB] Best Practice Note on Conflicts of Interest
 - review before each meeting, where decisions and/or recommendations are being made, whether there are any interests which may conflict with their duties as members of [Body] and, if so, disclose them to the co-chairs and supporting IPO staff
 - be asked by the Co-chairs of [Body] at each such meeting to confirm they have carried out such a review and made such disclosure
 - not participate in any activity of [Body] in relation to which they believe they have a conflict or possible conflict of interest without the consent of the [Body] Co-chairs, who will manage the conflict in accordance with the Best Practice Note.
7. Decision making is by consensus. However, if this is not possible, a vote should be taken. For a decision to be approved, there must be a 2/3 majority vote with 75% quorum of Voting Members.
 - 7.1. The Parent Body should be notified of any significant decisions within the annual report (see 28). In some circumstances, particularly where there are significant community coordination/resources implications, the Body may wish to seek endorsement from the Parent Body for a decision.
 - 7.2. If a decision from the Body is pending on Parent Body approval, and the Parent Body Liaison member(s) doesn't not answer within 1 month and after 2 reminders, the decision can be considered as approved. The last reminder must state that *"the decision will be considered as approved in absence of answer by [a given date], as per the Terms of Reference"*.
8. Members of the Body will:
 - 8.1. have regard to the [ESMO Conflict of Interest Policy](#).
 - 8.2. review before each meeting, where decisions and/or recommendations are being made, whether there are any interests which may conflict with their duties as members of Body and, if so, disclose them to the co-chairs and supporting IPO staff using the [Declaration of Conflict of Interest form](#).

- 8.3. be asked by the Co-chairs of Body at each meeting to confirm they have carried out such a review and made such disclosure.
- 8.4. not participate in any activity of the Body in relation to which they believe they have a conflict or possible conflict of interest without the consent of the Co-chairs, who will manage the conflict in accordance with the [ESMO Conflict of Interest Policy](#).

SIZE

9. In accordance with the ESMO ToRs, membership consists of two co-chairs, a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 15 members, including the voting members and co-chairs. Emeritus and ex-officio members can be appointed if needed. Emeritus and ex-officio members do not count within the maximum member number.

TERM, TERMINATION & EXTENSION

10. In alignment with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) (WCRP guidelines) all appointments are initially for a maximum of 4 years, with up to two 2-year extensions possible.
11. The four year terms of the two co-chairs shall be staggered by at least one calendar year as far as possible to prevent gaps in leadership and enhance resilience.
 - 11.1. When an existing member moves up to chair or co-chair, the appointment length “clock” is reset, with the condition that the member can serve on the committee up to a maximum of 10 years altogether. Only in rare circumstances (which would require ESMO SSG approval) would any individual serve on the same committee for longer than 10 years. Permission to do so must be sought from the Parent Body using the form in Annex B.
 - 11.2. For an outgoing chair or co-chair, an extension of up to 1 year as a voting member is possible, where a handover period is deemed necessary concurrently with the first year of a successor co-chair.
 - 11.3. Outgoing chairs/co-chairs, along with any other members who have exceeded their term, can be made Emeritus members at the discretion of the current co-chairs and Parent Body Liaison member(s).
12. Emeritus members have their membership reviewed annually, there is no limit on this term.
13. The relevance of ex-officio membership is reviewed every 4 years.
14. All members can resign from their position at any point and are encouraged to give a 3 months’ notice. Resigning members are encouraged to first discuss their circumstances with a chair/co-chairs. It might be more suitable to pause the membership in circumstances where ability to participate is restricted for a specific period of time (e.g., parental leave), or change the membership type. A membership pause is excluded from the service calculation in 10.1.

MEMBER APPOINTMENT

15. Co-chairs, voting and emeritus members are appointed on the basis of their personal experience and expertise and should be willing to represent relevant geographical or specialist science/technical areas, as set out in the membership call text and table of Body members (25).
16. All new appointments should be made with consideration of compliance with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) on diversity. Restrictions may be included to address underrepresentation within the Body. An open call should be issued by the ESMO IPO with a specification of requirements in line with membership responsibilities set by the co-chairs.

The open call should run for at least a month. A deadline will be set for applications, which will be collected by the ESMO IPO. The ESMO [or CMIP] IPO will coordinate all open calls for all ESMO [or CMIP] bodies, which can be requested through standard reporting mechanisms or by special need.

17. All applications should contain as a minimum:
 - a. A statement (up to 500 words) demonstrating why they are a good candidate for that position
 - b. A 1 page Curriculum Vitae (CV)
18. For voting member positions, the applications will be collected by ESMO IPO [or CMIP IPO for CMIP panel & WIP] and issued to the selection committee to make a decision. Decision options are Appoint, Waitlist and Reject. Applicants should be excluded from any selection committees/votes relating to this process.
 - 18.1. For regular members positions, the co-chairs are responsible for the selection. A shortlist of minimum two candidates and maximum three candidates should be provided in priority order from 1 (with 1 being the first choice). The length of the shortlist can be extended if several positions are available. The Parent Body Liaison member(s) either approves or proposes a new ranking until agreement with the co-chairs is reached.
 - 18.2. For Chair/Co-chair positions, the whole Body is responsible for the selection. A shortlist of maximum three candidates should be provided in priority order from 1 (with 1 being the first choice). The Parent Body co-chairs either approve or propose a new ranking until agreement with the Body is reached.
19. Members involved in shortlisting can refer to the ESMO SSG for arbitration.
20. No communication to candidates can take place until Parent Body Liaison member(s) approval has been obtained. Once obtained and the candidate has accepted the position, the Nomination form in Annex B should be completed.

REVOKING MEMBERSHIP

21. Unproductive members may be removed by the Body co-chairs if any of the following criteria are met:
 - 21.1. Two unexcused absences in consecutive meetings
 - 21.2. Violation of the [WCRP code of conduct](#)
 - 21.3. Undeclared conflict of interest
22. All member removals, including the reasoning for the removal and a copy of the removal communication, must be shared with the ESMO Parent Body and the ESMO IPO.

Roles and Responsibilities

23. It is the responsibility of all members to ensure the activities of the Body are in accordance with the goal and objectives set out in (3) and (4).
24. It is the responsibility of all members to ensure the Project Office supporting their activity has up to date contact details for them and is notified of any changes to role and employing institution.

25. Co-chairs are responsible for reviewing the table of member types every two years. Any amendments to the table should be issued as a new version of this ToR (45).

26. **TABLE: MEMBER TYPES OF [BODY], limited to 5-15 Members by (8)**

<i>MEMBER TYPE</i>	<i>APPOINTMENT PROCESS</i>	<i>TERM</i>	<i>RESPONSIBILITIES /JUSTIFICATION</i>
CO-CHAIRS	Open Call	Minimum 2 years	Lead of the body
VOTING MEMBER	Open Call	4+2+2	Active contribution to body functioning Some panels might have specific roles they outline here per member
EX-OFFICIO	Body & Parent Body Liaison member(s)	Reviewed every 4 years	Provide linkage to specified body/other activities
EMERITUS	Body & Parent Body Liaison member(s) (annual review)	1 y annually renewed	Provide historical knowledge and experienced insight

Meetings and deliverables

27. The Body shall meet virtually or in person at least once every 6 months, once every 3 months recommended, as a minimum.

28. An annual meeting with the Parent Body will be held with the Body co-chairs.

29. An annual report will be supplied to the Parent Body in the format and timeframe requested by them, in line with JSC reporting requirements. This will set out the achievements, significant decisions and recommendations, issues, plans, membership, and financial requests for the next 2 years and updates on Subsidiary Bodies.

Publications

30. All official publications of any activity within ESMO, with the exception of those controlled by the CMIP IPO and, or, academic, or professional publishers, must be published by the ESMO IPO. Where the ESMO IPO has delegated the publication to another IPO, the ESMO IPO must have sight of the final version prior to publication. Publications co-authored by members as part of the Body goals and objectives published by an ordinary peer-reviewing publisher should be provided to the relevant IPO and included in the annual report.

Code of conduct

31. All activities of the Body, and its representations on behalf of it by its members and members of its subsidiary bodies, must be made in compliance with the [WCRP Code of Conduct](#).

Subsidiary Bodies

TASK TEAMS

32. The [Body] may set up a Task Team. Notification of a Task Team creation should be submitted by the co-chairs to ESMO SSG following a specific template (see Annex A).
33. Recommendations for stand-alone ESMO Task Teams should be submitted to the ESMO SSG for approval prior to initiation. It is anticipated that approval will be granted within 30 working days of receipt of Notification.
34. Each Task Team should have at least one voting member of the Body as a Task Team member. Non-members, deemed associates, can be added. A list of members should be held by the co-chairs and the supporting project office.
35. Task Team activities must comply with the Body's terms of reference. The voting member(s) on the Task Team are responsible for this compliance.
36. It is recommended that each Task Team has two co-leads appointed for resilience. These can be self appointed or appointed through an open call, as deemed appropriate by the Body.
37. If a Task Team has delivered on the task(s) assigned, the team will be closed and letters of thanks issued from the co-chairs to the Task Team members in recognition of their contribution.
38. Should a Task Team be unable to progress delivery of the assigned task(s) or adjudication be required, the lead must report this to the Body co-chairs.

Amendments to the ToR

39. Any recommendations for amendments to the Terms of Reference should be submitted to the Parent Body for approval and validated by the ESMO SSG. This should include a cover table, using this template, providing a summary of the changes from the approved ToRs:

Page# #	Section Title, Clause	Change Description	Rationale/Justification

VERSION RECORD

Version number	Approval body	Date approved
Version 1	ESMO SSG	01.12.2024
Version 2		

ANNEX A

ESMO Task Team creation template

This template is to be completed and returned to ipo@wcrp-esmo.org

1. Name of the Task Team
2. Referent Working Group or Project Panel
3. Current members
4. Starting date
5. Planned duration
6. Purpose & objectives
7. Expected outcome
8. Linkage with existing ESMO activities or other WCRP activities if any

ANNEX B

Nomination for [Appointment/Extension]

Nominated for: [Name of the WCRP high-level steering committee]

As: [role of the nominated person, e.g., co-chair, member...]

1. DETAILS OF CANDIDATE NOMINATED

- Title:
- First Name:
- Last Name:
- Year of PhD (or the final academic degree) obtained:
- Residing country:
- Affiliation:
- E-mail Address:

2. MEMBER SINCE & UNTIL (year, in case of extension)

- Expertise vis-à-vis the role of the [WCRP core activity] (maximum of 8 lines):
- Science Background (maximum of 8 lines):
- Positions held (maximum of 8 lines):
- 5 most relevant publications
- Why is this individual particularly suited to this [steering committee]? (maximum of 5 lines)

3. SUBMITTED BY

- Title:
- First Name:
- Last Name:
- Organisation: